

DESIGNING FIBRE SHAPE TO IMPROVE OUT-OF-PLANE PERFORMANCE IN COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Composite materials are increasingly used for primary load bearing components in aerospace applications. Their poor through thickness properties are a major concern for their wider use. Existing approaches to improving these properties have a number of key limitations. A new approach, based upon fibres of novel cross-section, is currently being evaluated.

The fibres used in advanced continuous fibre reinforced plastics either have, or are considered to have, a circular cross section. Whilst it has been pointed out that fibre shape is a variable in the effective bonding between matrix and fibre, little work has been done to actively manipulate the shape and exploit potential benefits. Correct selection of the fibre shape could allow extensive load transfer by mechanical interlocking of the fibres and matrix as well as by interfacial bonding over a larger surface area.

Pre-impregnated epoxy tape was produced using shaped fibres. The tape was laid up into test coupons for fracture toughness tests (Mode I - $0^\circ/0^\circ$, $0^\circ/45^\circ$ and $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces). Similar tape was made with circular glass fibres and identical test coupons laid up for comparison. The Mode I fracture toughness testing indicates that shaped fibre composite can provide >20% improvement over circular fibres.

KEYWORDS: fibre shape, through-thickness, fracture toughness, strain energy release rate.

INTRODUCTION

As uses for fibre-reinforced polymer composites widen, there has been increasing interest in use of thicker sections [1] which result in significant through-thickness loads that cannot be neglected as is the case with thin shells. There are also a range of common structural features that lead to through-the-thickness loads which include: free edges, notches, ply drops, bonded joints and bolted joints.

The through thickness failure of FRP parts, often via delamination, has become a key design driver for aerospace engineers who are keen to exploit their excellent in-plane properties. The current damage tolerant philosophy states that a structure should sustain lifetime design loads in a damaged condition up to that at which 'barely visible' impact damage is detectable. Thus the design allowable ultimate strain is limited to about 0.4%. Improvement of this aspect of damage tolerance will enable the use of higher allowable design strains of 0.5-0.6%, producing further weight savings compared to existing CFRP systems [2]. Excellent review papers of existing approaches to improving the through-thickness properties of composites are widely available in the literature [2-8].

In the pursuit of increasing the toughness/delamination resistance of FRPs, compromises have always been made against other mechanical properties [2,3,6]. It is recognised that a loss of in-plane performance is acceptable if the design drivers are for greater through-thickness performance [5]. However, an approach that avoids such a compromise is sought to fully exploit the potential of FRPs for engineers seeking to produce high strength optimised structures. The cross-sectional shape of reinforcing fibres within FRPs can potentially provide such a solution [9,10].

The earliest assessment of the effect of fibre shape upon continuous FRPs, following Tsai *et al.* [11], was work on non-mechanical aspects of FRP properties. Aditya & Sinha [12] describe the effect that the shape of carbon fibres has on moisture diffusion in their FRPs. Chand's review [13] of carbon fibres for composites comments that thin walled carbon fibres, specifically these H-shaped fibres but also C-shaped fibres, have improved carbon structure uniformity and fibre strength.

Deng *et al.* [14] undertook a characterisation study of two shaped glass fibres. They compared 'peanut' and 'flat' fibres to circular ones. Both fibres suffered preferred orientation during production of the laminate resulting in resin denudation between fibres leading to easier crack propagation. In their follow-up study [15], their results indicated that the fibre aspect ratio did not have a noticeable influence on the Interfacial Shear Strength of their composites. The Mode I, Mode II and ILSS tests all indicated a reduced delamination resistance for the 'peanut' and 'flat' shaped fibres. This was found to be a result of the fibre orientation phenomenon that had previously affected the in-plane tests. Hucker *et al.* [16] later compared triangular shaped fibre composites with those of circular fibres. Their reported increase in the compressive strength of the triangular fibres may be an artefact of the testing method. However, it may also have been that the such fibres were more resistant to micro-buckling because of their higher second moment of area.

Brady *et al.* [17] reported that transverse toughness is a more sensitive indicator of the state of a ply interface than transverse strength. The measurement of the Mode I fracture toughness below provides an opportunity to further assess the state of the ply interface in shaped fibre laminates. The Mode I fracture toughness testing was carried out in accordance with the ESIS standard [18]. Although delamination in laminates is most often caused under Mode II loading the simplicity of Mode I testing made it the obvious first step in a comparative study of toughness.

MATERIALS

The Aerospace department at Bristol has a proven [19-22] capability in the manufacture of hollow and novel shaped glass fibres and their composites. The facilities include a bespoke glass fibre drawing tower. The tower allows glass preforms to be heated and drawn to the required dimensions for fibre reinforcing applications. A schematic of the fibre drawing tower is shown in Fig. 1. This configuration allows shaped fibre to be manufactured with specific diameters via careful control of temperature, preform feed and fibre draw rates, assuming a constant volume flow.

Reinforcing fibre (Fig. 2a) was wound onto a drum at the bottom of the drawing tower until a sufficient volume was prepared to facilitate manufacture of an epoxy resin preimpregnated tape. Hexcel 913 epoxy resin film (42 gsm) was applied to the fibres on the drum by a simple overlaying process to form a 'prepreg' tape. This 'prepreg' sheet was then subjected to a full atmospheric vacuum for 45 minutes at 80°C to encourage resin impregnation into the fibre layer. At this stage the 'prepreg' sheet is suitable for use with conventional polymer

composite manufacturing techniques. The laminate plates (Fig. 2b) for testing were produced by an autoclave curing process. The manufacturers recommended 1 hour dwell at $120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and at a pressure of 7 bar was used but with a preceding $90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ dwell for 30 minutes (recommended for parts in excess of 3mm thickness). The heating rate was $2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ which is within the manufacturer's recommended range. The cured laminate was allowed to cool passively within the autoclave at a rate well below the maximum.

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of the fibre drawing apparatus.

Fig. 2: (a) Six lobed shaped glass fibres with an outermost diameter of $50\text{ }\mu\text{m}$, (b) a transverse section through a composite plate of the same fibres in a 913 epoxy matrix.

METHODOLOGY

The ESIS standard [18] for the determination of Mode I fracture toughness utilises a Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimen (Fig. 3). Load-blocks were attached with a two-part epoxy (ARALDITE™ 2010) which exceeded the bonding requirement of the standard. PTFE starter film ($10\mu\text{m}$ thickness) was used to ensure correct crack initiation along the interface of interest in the non-unidirectional specimens that were tested. The standard specifies a correction factor to be applied in analysis that accounts for the movement of the effective loading position that the use of load blocks instigates.

The interlocking of shaped fibres is a possible mechanism of improving the through-thickness properties. Interlocking cannot occur at off-axis ply interfaces and so the effect of its presence or absence on fracture toughness needs to be examined. Mode I fracture toughness (G_{IC}) was

therefore measured for $0^\circ/0^\circ$, $0^\circ/45^\circ$ and $0^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces. The ESIS standard is, strictly speaking, only applicable to unidirectional specimens. However, the standard permits other lay-ups which satisfy a condition based upon the D-matrix (bending or flexural laminate stiffnesses relating moments to curvatures) of the plate stiffness matrix from classical lamination theory [23]:

$$\frac{D_{12}^2}{D_{11}D_{22}} \ll 1 \quad (1)$$

An increasing value of this ratio indicates an increasing bend-twist coupling which results in a severely curved delamination front that invalidates the fracture initiation values. Laminate stacking sequences for the interfaces investigated are shown in Table 1.

Fig. 3: Schematic drawing of (a) DCB Mode I fracture toughness specimen, and (b) load blocks.

Table 1: The lay-up of the DCB specimens.

Test	Lay-up
DCB $0^\circ/0^\circ$	$[0_{8C}^\circ / 0_{8I}^\circ // 0_{8I}^\circ / 0_{8C}^\circ]$
DCB $0^\circ/45^\circ$	$[0_I^\circ / -45_I^\circ / 45_I^\circ / 0_I^\circ / 0_{8I}^\circ / 0_I^\circ / -45_I^\circ / 45_I^\circ / 0_I^\circ // 45_I^\circ / 0_I^\circ / 0_I^\circ / -45_I^\circ / 0_{8I}^\circ / 45_I^\circ / 0_I^\circ / 0_I^\circ / -45_I^\circ]$
DCB $0^\circ/90^\circ$	$[90_C^\circ / 0_{2C}^\circ / 90_C^\circ / 0_C^\circ / 90_{2C}^\circ / 0_C^\circ / 0_I^\circ / 90_{2I}^\circ / 0_I^\circ / 90_I^\circ / 0_{2I}^\circ / 90_I^\circ // 0_I^\circ / 90_{2I}^\circ / 0_I^\circ / 90_I^\circ / 0_{2I}^\circ / 90_I^\circ / 90_C^\circ / 0_{2C}^\circ / 90_C^\circ / 0_C^\circ / 90_{2C}^\circ / 0_C^\circ]$

The subscript represents the number of plies and the type of fibres (C – commercial; I – In-house) and // denotes the position of the precrack where present.

Due to the limited quantities of material the laminate specimens were 3mm thick (Fig.2) which is less than the 5mm recommendation for 60% by volume glass fibre reinforced composites. Consequently some large deflections were seen and the appropriate Large Deflection Correction Factor (Clause 8.3 [17]) from the ESIS standard was applied. A review of fracture toughness testing [23] confirms the suitability of the DCB specimen for Mode I fracture toughness testing. A careful choice of lay-up in non-UD specimens (Table 1) can minimise the effects of residual stress, mixed mode fracture and curved delamination fronts. The standard allows for the measurement of the crack position to be determined from a surface rather than the edge in the case of ‘translucent’ specimens. The crack position was far clearer viewed through the surface than from the edge. A paper scale was attached to the upper surface of the specimen. A lamp was positioned beneath the specimen, to enhance the crack front but offset at an angle to minimise any heating of the specimen. The crack was measured from the loaded end of the specimen against the scale with the assistance of a

magnifying lens. This measurement, as well as the concurrent load and displacement which could be held on their digital displays, were recorded verbally and later transcribed for analysis. Testing was carried out using an Instron 4507 test machine with a 200kN load cell at a rate of 2.0 mm min⁻¹.

RESULTS

Method Anomalies

The PTFE starter film (10 μ m) extended only 30mm past the load-line rather than the required 50mm as a result of incorrect positioning of the starter film during lay-up. The standard [18] states that this may have allowed the load-blocks to have an effect on initiation and propagation values up to crack lengths of 70 mm. Tests for initiation values were made for the first specimens but were found to be similar or identical to the propagation values up to and beyond crack lengths of 70 mm. Subsequently the initiation values, which must be viewed with caution because of the short starter films, were recorded as part of the crack propagation tests. Slight permanent opening deformation was noticed in all the specimens after testing. This is likely to be due to a combination of crack branching during the testing and residual stresses from manufacture that were released by the fracture process.

Graphical Results

Fig.'s 4-6 summarise the Mode I fracture toughness results for crack propagation in the 0°/0°, 0°/45° and 0°/90° interfaces respectively. These plots include an overlaid moving average. This is the mean fracture toughness of all the specimens from a laminate with a crack length of +/-4mm from the stated value. The mean of each of these moving averages, with the volume fraction, is given in Table 2 for the 0°/0°, 0°/45° and 0°/90° interfaces respectively.

Table 2: Summary of DCB results.

DCB Interface	Fibre Type	Mean Fracture Toughness MPa	Co-efficient of Variation %	Volume Fraction %	% Difference
0°/0°	Shaped	215.7	15.7	52.3	67.1
	Circular	129.1	15.9	52.8	
0°/45°	Shaped	169.3	14.8	52.8	-17.0
	Circular	203.9	25.1	52.0	
0°/90°	Shaped	167.2	13.1	53.5	55.5
	Circular	107.2	16.3	54.7	

Numerical Results

The ESIS standard specifies two analysis approaches – Corrected Beam Theory (CBT) and Experimental Compliance Method (ECM). Fig. 7 provides a comparison of CBT and ECM for the first circular and shaped specimen of the 0°/0° interface specimens. There is a nearly constant proportional difference between the values predicted by the methods of 19% for the circular specimen and 18% for the shaped. Although this affected the absolute values significantly it does not affect the comparison of shaped and circular specimens significantly. The Corrected Beam Theory was chosen for all other plots although there was little to distinguish the methods. The choice was based upon the slight relative advantage it gave the circular fibre specimens which exhibited the lowest fracture toughness values measured.

Figure 4: DCB 0°/0°, circular fibres indicated by circles and shaped fibres by asterisks.

Figure 5: DCB 0°/45°, circular fibres indicated by circles and shaped fibres by asterisks.

Figure 6: DCB 0°/90°, circular fibres indicated by circles and shaped fibres by asterisks.

Figure 7: Comparison of CBT and ECM for the 1st circular and shaped 0°/0° interface specimens.

Results Anomalies

The 0°/45° specimens were laid up with thinner sub-laminates of in-house produced plies around the interface than the specimens for the other interfaces. Sufficient in-house and commercial material was not available to provide an alternative balanced lay-up. A balanced lay-up was necessary to ensure that the sub-laminates created by the crack did not exhibit bend-twist coupling. These 0°/45° specimens were the last to be manufactured and the insignificant crack deviation in the previous 0°/0° and 0°/90° tests suggested that the thinner central sublaminates at the centre of the 0°/45° specimens would not interfere with the intended crack propagation. However, the first set of tests upon circular fibres generated spurious results. Unlike the previously tested specimens the apparent fracture toughness did not exhibit an initial peak and subsequent drop-off with increasing crack length. Rather the toughness of the circular fibre specimens either continually increased or rose to a maximum halfway through crack propagation. The shaped fibre specimens all exhibited the previously

observed norm of an initial peak and subsequent drop-off but with an final increase in toughness towards the end of crack propagation.

DISCUSSION

Fibre bridging only occurred in the circular fibre $0^\circ/45^\circ$ specimens, and even then it was limited to a region behind the crack front that was approximately 5mm in length. Pereira & Morais [24] observed an R-curve, i.e. increasing fracture toughness with increasing crack length, in their Double Cantilever Beam testing of $0^\circ/\theta^\circ$ interfaces in carbon fibre reinforced epoxy. They attributed this behaviour to fibre bridging. The initiation values in the present work, for all but the circular fibre $0^\circ/45^\circ$ specimens, are very similar to the propagation values as indicated by Fig. 4 and Fig. 65. This is consistent with the absence of fibre bridging. The initiation values may be somewhat distorted by the slight disturbance of the fibres that the starter crack may have caused as well as the additional stiffness of the loading tabs located so close to the point of initiation.

Interface Angle

Shetty *et al.* [25] found that an increasing ply angle θ° in a $\theta^\circ/-\theta^\circ$ interface led to an increased G_{Ic} . Pereira & Morais [24] found that G_{Ic} initiation values for $0^\circ/\theta^\circ$ interfaces were independent of θ° and that propagation values were dominated by fibre bridging, an artefact of DCB testing. Tao & Sun [26] showed that an increasing ply angle θ° in a $0^\circ/\theta^\circ$ interface led to a decreased G_{IIc} . And Foster *et al.* [27] found no angle dependence for mixed Mode I/II (G_{Ic}/G_{IIc}). A review of published data [23] suggested that when data scatter is considered the interface lay-up does not affect the G_{Ic} initiation value. They limited their review to initiation values because of the impact that fibre bridging has on crack propagation. However, in the present work there was no fibre bridging evident to distort propagation values. Indeed, the propagation values are the more unreliable for the reasons already described, i.e. distance from the load blocks and from the starter film as well the consistency of the measured values. Thus, interface angle does not seem to be a significant variable in Mode I fracture toughness initiation values nor for propagation values where fibre bridging does not occur. However, it was predicted that the absence of interlocking between shaped fibres at off axis interfaces might manifest itself in a step change of fracture toughness from the $0^\circ/0^\circ$ interface value.

The initial set of $0^\circ/45^\circ$ were the only specimens to show evidence of fibre bridging and examination with a Scanning Electron Microscope clearly showed that the crack had passed along a number of the circular ply interfaces as evidenced by the signs of 0° , 45° and -45° fibres (Fig. 8). In comparison the shaped fibre crack appears to have passed along the correct interface and shows only signs of 0° and 45° fibres (Fig. 9). At initiation i.e. before bridging could occur, the fracture toughness of the shaped fibre specimens was, as in all other instances, superior to the circular fibres. The ply and laminate production records showed that there had been some concern over the performance of the sizing applicator during the production of the prepreg plies used to make the circular fibre laminate. It is possible that a reduced amount of size was applied to the circular fibres. They would have been predisposed to disbond from the surrounding matrix under loading that in all other specimens appears to have itself fractured. This may have led to the fibre bridging and thus the apparent increase in the fracture toughness. The fibre bridging persisted for the complete duration of crack propagation in most cases and caused excessive deflection of the specimen arms.

Fig. 8: Typical DCB circular specimen 0°/45° interface fracture surface. Note: extensive propagation on the +45° & -45° plies.

Fig. 9: Typical DCB shaped specimen 0°/45° interface fracture surface. Note: only narrow strips of propagation on the +45° layer.

The fracture toughness of the 0°/45° shaped fibre specimens appears to be consistent with the 0°/0° and 0°/90° tests. Although there is no corresponding data for the circular fibre specimens (due to the problems with the 0°/45° circular specimens reported above) the initiation values exist for both and are compared directly in Table 3. These values are based upon the mean load, displacement and crack length for the visible propagation and maximum load points. These points were plotted, along with the non-linear initiation criterion and the ‘+5%’ compliance criterion for initiation, to verify that this was a fair representation of the initiation points. The shaped fibre specimens outperform the circular and there is no overlap between the sets of data although the difference between the mean (~21%) is smaller than that seen for the propagation values of the other interfaces.

Table 3: Initiation fracture toughness values for 0°/45° specimens determined from analysis of the load/deflection history.

Fibre Type	Specimen	Fracture Toughness kJ/m ²	Fibre Type	Specimen	Fracture Toughness kJ/m ²
Shaped 0°/45°	1	218	Circular 0°/45°	1	143
	2	198		2	149
	3	214		3	185
	4	220		4	185
	5	195		5	178
	6	203		6	191
	Mean	208		Mean	172
	CoV %	5.1		CoV %	12.0

Qualitative comparison of the fracture toughness plots for the 0°/0° and 0°/90° confirms that this advantage in initiation fracture toughness is a general phenomenon. Comparison of the 0°/0° and 0°/90° fracture surfaces under an electron microscope clearly showed that the shaped fibres clearly generate a more tortuous fracture surface than the circular fibres (i.e. Fig. 10 vs. Fig. 11, Fig. 12 vs. Fig. 13).

Fracture Surface Morphology

A comparison of the circular and shaped fibre fracture surfaces (Fig.’s 10-13) clearly shows that the increased surface area of the shaped fibres leads to a rougher fracture surface of increased area. Lee & Suh [28] added micro-beads to their resin matrix which created extra crack surface area in DCB specimens. The initiation fracture toughness was improved but propagation was lowered. They identified the suppression of fibre bridging, due to the micro-

beads, as the reason for these reduced values. The extra crack surface in the shaped fibre specimens is the simplest explanation for the increased fracture toughness that they possess.

Figure 10: Circular 0°/0° interface showing hackling but not as much as shaped.

Figure 11: Shaped 0°/0° interface showing hackling.

Figure 12: Circular 0°/90° interface showing circular gullies and cracks running through interlaminar (not ply edges) region unlike shaped.

Figure 13: Shaped 0°/90° interface showing extensive grooving and implications of ply edge cracking unlike circular.

CONCLUSIONS

- The DCB testing results show that, in general, the shaped fibre specimens have a significantly greater (>50%) strain energy release rate (G_{Ic}) than equivalent circular fibre specimens for 0°/0°, 0°/45° and 0°/90° interfaces.
- Despite the problematic 0°/45° circular fibre specimens, a comparison of $G_{Ic(\text{initiation})}$ for shaped and circular confirms the greater values for the former by approximately 20%.
- The more pronounced ‘hackle’ markings on the fracture surfaces of the shaped fibre specimens suggests that their interface strength is indeed superior. This is coupled with the greater crack tortuosity for the shaped fibre specimens in which the cracks sporadically followed the more tortuous fibre-matrix interface of the shaped fibres.

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